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EVOLUTION OF CRUDE EXTRACT AND FRACTIONS OF *Camellia sinensis* LEAVES AGAINST HUMAN PATHOGENIC BACTERIAL STRAINS

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to find out the antibacterial activity of individual crude extract and fraction and mixture active fraction of *Camellia sinensis*. For antibacterial test, disc diffusion technique was used against human pathogenic bacterial strains. The noteworthy inhibition of ethanol mixed methanol active fraction was inhibit 7 mm zone against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and 8 mm zone against *Staphylococcus aureus*, it was higher activity than all individual fractions and crude extract. In the GC-MS analysis, 20 bioactive phytochemical compounds were identified in the ethanolic fraction of *Camellia sinensis*. Further work needs to be done in these materials including fractionation to isolate active constituents and subsequent pharmacological evaluation.

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INTRODUCTION

Plant active compounds are of new attention as antiseptics and antimicrobial agents. Because of numerous synthetic drugs are withdrawn years after their introduction into the market due to their adverse side effects, while increasing resistance to antibiotics of many bacteria [1, 2]. *Camellia sinensis* is a member of the Theaceae. It is highly containing large amounts of polyphenols, and it could also be significant source of those constituents in human diet [3]. Phytochemical investigations of *Camellia sinensis* have been reported on the lipids, alkaloids, steroids, tannins, polyphenols, terpenoids, flavonoids and Saponins [4]. In particular, *Camellia sinensis* leaves have exhibited significant antibacterial activity [5]. Hence forward, we had tried to determine the antimicrobial activity of *Camellia sinensis* leaves against *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

The epidemiology of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, a major cause of meningitis, pneumonia, bacteraemia and acute otitis media in both children and adults [6]. Clinicians and microbiologists have resisted developing tests that can identify pneumococcal respiratory infection and accurately discriminate colonization from invasive disease [7]. *Staphylococcus aureus* are a major clinical problem owing to the high incidence of soft tissue infections and the widespread emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains [8].

The objective of this study is to find active fraction from *Camellia sinensis* that are used to treat against human pathogenic bacterial strains *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate from severe disease affected patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material:

Healthy and young leaves (3-6 months old) of *Camellia sinensis* were collected from Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India. The leaves were separated from stems, washed in clean water, and dried at room temperature. The shaded dried leaves were weighed and ground in a sterile mortar.

Extraction:

The shade dried plant material was cut into small pieces and finally crushed into fine powder. 500g of powdered plant material was soaked and then extracted successively with water, ethanol, methanol, acetone, hexane and butanol solvent in separate Soxhlet's extractor for 48h. The extract was concentrated to dryness in rotary vacuum evaporator and stored at -30°C until further use.

Fractionation:

500g of powdered plant material was soaked and then extracted with ethanol in a Soxhlet's apparatus. After, collected extracts were evaporated to dryness in desiccators. After, these crude extracts were fractionated with water, ethanol, methanol, acetone, hexane and butanol using column chromatography under reduced pressure over silica gel. These fractions were then stored in a refrigerator until used for the phytochemical and antimicrobial screening.

Micro organisms:

Bacterial culture of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were clinical isolates of patients isolated from clinical patients at dental clinics in and around Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India.

Determination of antimicrobial activity:

Culture supernatants with fractions and crude extract of the plants were used in the disc-diffusion method separately. *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were swabbed on the surface of the Sabouraud agar plates and discs (Whatman No.1 filter paper with 9 mm diameter) impregnated with the 50 µl of each plant sample was placed on the surface individually. To compare the anti-bacterial activities, Nystatin (20 µg/disc) used as standard antibiotic and negative control, a blank disc impregnated with solvent followed by drying was used. The plates (triplicates) were incubated at 28°C for 72 h. The antimicrobial potency of the test samples was measured by determining the diameter of the zones of inhibition in millimeter.

GC-MS analysis:

50 g powdered sample of *Camellia sinensis* were soaked and dissolved in 75 ml of methanol for 24 h. Then the filtrates were collected by evaporated under liquid nitrogen. The GC-MS analysis was carried out using a Clarus 500 Perkin-Elmer (Auto System XL) Gas Chromatograph equipped and coupled to a mass detector Turbo mass gold – Perkin Elmer Turbomas 5.2 spectrometer with an Elite-1 (100% Dimethyl polysiloxane), 300 m x 0.25 mm x 1 µm df capillary column. The instrument was set to an initial temperature of 110°C, and maintained at this temperature for 2 min. At the end of this period, the oven temperature was raised up to 280°C, at the rate of an increase of 5°C/min, and maintained for 9 min. Injection port temperature was ensured as 250°C and Helium flow rate as 1 ml/min. The ionization voltage was 70 eV. The samples were injected in split mode as 10:1. Mass Spectral scan range was set at 45- 450 (m/z). The chemical constituents were identified by GC-MS. The fragmentation patterns of mass spectra were compared with those stored in the spectrometer database using National Institute of Standards and Technology Mass Spectral database (NIST-MS). The percentage of each component was calculated from relative peak area of each component in the chromatogram.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

In disc diffusion method all the individual fractions and crude extracts showed inhibitory response against both organisms are examined (Table 1 and 2). The 0.5, 1, 3, 0.5, 1, 0.5 mm inhibition zone by extract and 2, 3, 2, 1, 1, 0.5 mm inhibition zone by fraction activity against *Streptococcus pneumonia* and to 2, 4, 3, 1, 1, 0.5 mm and 2, 5, 4, 0.5, 1, 3 mm inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* by action of extract and fraction was studied. The substantial activity was observed in methanol and ethanol fraction, which was selected and over again various combinations to treat new *Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus* strains (Table 3). 4:16 combination of ethanolic methanol fraction was 7 mm zone inhibition activity against *Streptococcus pneumonia* and 10:10 combination make 8 mm zone inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* strain, which was further comparable with that of standard antibiotic Nystatin. Whereas, the crude extract of different solvent did not show significant inhibition activity.

Table 1: Antimicrobial activity of *Camellia sinensis* individual solvent crude extract tested against *Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Plant sample/ Solvent	Zone of inhibition (mm)					
	Water	Ethanol	Methanol	Acetone	Hexane	Butanol
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	0.5	1	3	0.5	1	0.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2	4	3	1	1	0.5

This was supported by a previous study on an alcoholic extract that exhibited greater activity than the aqueous and hexane extracts against bacteria, with no cellular toxicity [9]. The broad spectrum of antibacterial activity was reported for *T. chebula* [10] and *T. Arjuna* [11]. The ethanol extract at a concentration of 1 mg/disc showed maximum inhibition against *S. epidermidis*, followed by *B. subtilis*.

Table 2: Antimicrobial activity of *Camellia sinensis* individual fraction tested against *Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by disc diffusion method.

Plant sample/ Solvent	Zone of inhibition (mm)					
	Water	Ethanol	Methanol	Acetone	Hexane	Butanol
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	2	3	2	1	1	0.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2	5	4	0.5	1	3

Table 3: Antimicrobial activity of ethanol and methanol combined fractions of *Camellia Sinensis* tested against *Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by disc diffusion method.

Plant sample/ Fraction concentration	Zone of inhibition (mm)									
	18:2 (E/M)	16:4 (E/M)	14:6 (E/M)	12:8 (E/M)	10:10 (E/M)	8:12 (E/M)	6:14 (E/M)	4:16 (E/M)	2:18 (E/M)	
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	2	0.5	1	6	3	2	0.5	7	4	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1	2	2	1	8	2	1	0.5	7	

In addition, GC-MS analysis, totally 20 compounds identified from the methanol fractions of the *Camellia sinensis* presented in Table 4. The plant samples revealed the synthesis of 1,2,5,6-Tetrahydropyridin-2-one, 5-methyl, 2, 3-Pentanedione, 4-methyl-3H-Pyrazol-3-one, 2, 4-dihydro-2, 4, 5-trimethyl, 1, 2, 5, 6-Tetrahydropyridin-2-one, 5-methyl, 3-Amino-2-oxazolidinone, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2, 3-dihydro-2-[1-(benzyloxy)ethyl], 2-Methoxyresorcinol, Eugenol, Naphthalene, 6-ethyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-1, 1, 4, 4-tetramethyl-7-(1-methylethenyl), 1,2, 3-Benzenetriol, Sucrose, D-Allose, Oxalic acid, 2-ethylhexyl hexyl ester, Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptan-3-ol, 2, 6, 6-trimethyl, 3, 7, 11, 15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol, 1H-Purine-2, 6-dione, 3, 7-dihydro-1, 3, 7-trimethyl, 1H-Purine-2, 6-dione, 3, 7-dihydro-1, 3-dimethyl, Phytol, Myristoyl chloride and Squalene. All these compounds are of pharmacological importance as they possess the properties such as analgesic, anti-diabetic, antibacterial and antifungal.

Table 4: The main compounds identified by GC-MS in the extracts of the *Camellia sinensis*.

S.No.	Peak name	Retention time	Peak Area	%Peak Area
1	Name: 1,2,5,6-Tetrahydropyridin-2-one, 5-methyl- Formula: C ₆ H ₉ NO MW: 111	6.26	1507229	0.4019
2	Name: 2,3-Pentanedione, 4-methyl- Formula: C ₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ MW: 114	6.74	471922	0.1258
3	Name: 3H-Pyrazol-3-one, 2,4-dihydro-2,4,5-trimethyl- Formula: C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O MW: 126	7.39	1086150	0.2896
4	Name: 1,2,5,6-Tetrahydropyridin-2-one, 5-methyl- Formula: C ₆ H ₉ NO MW: 111	7.90	1455643	0.3882
5	Name: 3-Amino-2-oxazolidinone Formula: C ₃ H ₆ N ₂ O ₂ MW: 102	8.50	193891	0.0517
6	Name: 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-2-[1-(benzyloxy)ethyl]- Formula: C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ MW: 232	8.60	1165119	0.3107
7	Name: 2-Methoxyresorcinol Formula: C ₇ H ₈ O ₃ MW: 140	10.72	844408	0.2252
8	Name: Eugenol Formula: C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ MW: 164	12.17	486539	0.1297
9	Name: Naphthalene, 6-ethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1,1,4,4-tetramethyl-7-(1-methylethenyl)- Formula: C ₁₉ H ₂₈ MW: 256	12.91	705406	0.1881
10	Name: 1,2,3-Benzenetriol Formula: C ₆ H ₆ O ₃ MW: 126	13.36	5607427	1.4953
11	Name: Sucrose Formula: C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁ MW: 342	13.99	5238841	1.3970
12	Name: D-Allose Formula: C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆ MW: 180	15.30	548481	0.1463
13	Name: Oxalic acid, 2-ethylhexyl hexyl ester Formula: C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₄ MW: 286	17.70	11093346	2.9581
14	Name: Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptan-3-ol, 2,6,6-trimethyl- Formula: C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O MW: 154	17.91	3115463	0.8308
15	Name: 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol Formula: C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O MW: 296	20.08	2854328	0.7611
16	Name: 1H-Purine-2,6-dione, 3,7-dihydro-1,3,7-trimethyl- Formula: C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	20.79	324399328	86.5030

17	MW: 194 Name: 1H-Purine-2,6-dione, 3,7-dihydro-1,3-dimethyl- Formula: C7H8N4O2	21.18	7978280	2.1275
18	MW: 180 Name: Phytol Formula: C20H40O	23.23	2225372	0.5934
19	MW: 296 Name: Myristoyl chloride Formula: C14H27ClO	25.01	681042	0.1816
20	MW: 246 Name: Squalene Formula: C30H50 MW: 410	30.24	3356811	0.8951

Hence, from the foregoing discussion it may be concluded that *Camellia sinensis*, a common medicinal plant could be exploited as the source of a potent biocide that have immense bacteria toxic effect to several bacterial pathogens like *Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

CONCLUSION

Antibacterial activity of individual crude extract and fraction and mixture active fraction of *Camellia sinensis* was studied by paper disc method. On the account of that, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* showed inhibition of 7 mm and 8 mm zone against *Staphylococcus aureus* in ethanol mixed methanol active fraction. In future, it will be a strong chemotherapy drug and have treat against diseases.

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